

What is the Synchronisation Force?

A blueprint for sustaining a good practice

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Synchronising FAIR efforts within EOSC

The successive EC-funded projects FAIRsFAIR¹ and FAIR-IMPACT² both included a Synchronisation Force, which successfully organised annual workshops and, at the end of the projects, published a White Paper as a result of these workshops with recommendations for the wider FAIR and EOSC environment³. When asked about the main function of the Synchronisation Force, workshop participants gave answers like “a way to know what is going on and the possibility to provide comments” and “allowing convergence and harmonisation, avoiding duplication”. In addition, on average the workshop reports⁴ were downloaded more than 650 times each, while the FAIRsFAIR White Paper was downloaded more than 1200 times. In both projects the Synchronisation Force, or SF, was identified as a Key function, which is an important function performed by the project which requires sustainability measures during and after the project. FAIR-IMPACT sustained the SF from FAIRsFAIR, but who will sustain it now FAIR-IMPACT comes to an end⁵?

The goal

A Synchronisation Force is a team of experts dedicated to periodically bringing together initiatives that promote and work towards a common goal. The FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force is set up to maintain a dialogue across the complex EOSC and FAIR ecosystems so as to maximise collaboration and alignment. The SF aims to minimise redundancy and promote sustainable, widely accepted, and easily transferable solutions to the EOSC Partnership, facilitating the adoption of FAIR-enabling practices among current and future EOSC stakeholders.

¹ <https://fairsfair.eu/> and <https://fair-impact.eu/fairsfair-legacy>

² <https://fair-impact.eu/>

³ Dillo, I., Hodson, S., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., & Grootveld, M. (2021). D5.7 Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force 2021 (Version 1.0 Glossy). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6674042> The FAIR-IMPACT White Paper is under review.

⁴ The workshop reports 2019-2021 can be retrieved from <https://fair-impact.eu/fairsfair-legacy>. The workshop reports 2022-2024 can be retrieved from <https://fair-impact.eu/synchronisation-force>.

⁵ The remainder of this document is written in present tense, as inspiration for the next installment of the Synchronisation Force.

The Workshop participants and output

The Synchronisation Force team reaches out to EOSC Association Task Forces, Opportunity Area Expert Groups, FAIR champions, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, EOSC-building projects and EC Project Officers. The SF organises annual workshops as a series of online sessions, with representatives from 80-90 initiatives. Per year, the visualisation of the landscape of these initiatives is updated and used in the workshop to set the scene. Attendance is by invitation only, but with the option that invitees share the invitation with colleagues who can contribute more to certain topics. After each workshop series a concise report with core findings and recommendations is drafted, discussed with the workshop participants in a final session, and published. In addition to this tangible output, attendants appreciate hearing from each other about related and relevant developments. After three annual workshops, the Synchronisation Force looks back on the recommendations and discusses in a White Paper which core recommendations should be implemented, to align with EOSC strategic ambitions, for instance as formulated in the Multi-Annual Roadmaps.

The topics

While innumerable conversations can be held about “FAIR and EOSC”, the topics to discuss in the workshops are the core project topics, already selected in the proposal phase. See Figure 1 as an example.

Date	Session Topic	Chair & Rapporteur
26 September 10.00-11.30 CET	Metrics and assessing FAIRness	Chair: Mike Priddy, DANS Rapporteur: Maaïke Verburg, DANS
30 September 13.00-14.30 CET	Sustainability of project outputs	Chair: Ingrid Dillo, DANS Rapporteur: Marita Everhardt, DANS
1 October 10.00-11.30 CET	Persistent Identifiers	Chair: Josefine Nordling, CSC Rapporteur: Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen, CSC
3 October 10.00-11.30 CET	Legal & organisational interoperability	Chair: Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC Rapporteur: Olivier Rouchon, CNRS
3 October 14.00-15.30 CET	Trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories	Chair: Laurence Horton, DCC Rapporteur: Maaïke Verburg, DANS and Daniel Turner, DCC
8 October 14.00-15.30 CET	Metadata, semantics and interoperability	Chair: Esteban Gonzalez, UPM Rapporteur: Nina Grau, INRAE and Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC
7 November 10.00-11.30 CET	Plenary discussion session	

Figure 1. Overview of the SF Workshop 2024, presented in the introductory session

The invitation makes explicit that all participants are expected to attend the introductory session. Here they hear about the topics to come, but perhaps more importantly, they learn that they have to provide information about FAIR developments in their project or initiative before attending these topical sessions.

The organising SF team

The SF is composed of experts from the project: the Work Package leaders plus one secondant from each Work Package. Each year, they identify per topic the currently relevant questions to discuss. Typically, these questions refer to new or updated EOSC-related strategic documents, as well as to findings or recommendations from the year before. The latter is especially important in order to take stock of progress.

Next, the SF decides per topic who they will invite to give a so-called conversation starter. This is a 5-minute introduction to set the stage and invite responses, preferably without presentation slides. Slightly guided discussion is the core of each 90-minute topical session. Behind the scenes the SF arranges for note-taking, which is the basis for the annual workshop report. In all, FAIR-IMPACT reserves 8 person months per year for the SF.

What makes this different from other project meetings?

1. By providing the workshop each year, the SF allows participants to identify and highlight progress over time. An indication that this was appreciated at the time of FAIRsFAIR and FAIR-IMPACT is the fact that most initiatives, up to the level of individual participants, attended several years in row.
2. The variety of stakeholder categories that join the workshops is extremely rich.
3. All sessions offer a stage for FAIR-related contributions from workshop participants, such as tools, services, deliverables, events or training provided by other European projects and initiatives. The SF workshops do intentionally not center around output from the organising project.
4. The workshops come with 'homework': All participants are expected to share information about FAIR tools, services, reports and events that their initiative has delivered or plans to deliver. For this, the SF provides a huge spreadsheet. Typically, only a few attendants provide this information timely, that is, ahead of the topical sessions; others will follow once they recognise that this 'homework' makes their work more visible.

Scenarios for continuation

Project funding allowed FAIRsFAIR and FAIR-IMPACT to run the Synchronisation Force and achieve the results mentioned above. In this section we sketch two scenarios to continue to synchronise FAIR efforts across many initiatives with limited effort: one face-to-face scenario and one scenario focussing on written output.

1. A Synchronisation Day attached to the EOSC Winter School

At the EOSC Winter School representatives of many European projects come together who are eager to discuss and advance their projects.

- ***Target audience:*** European projects, EOSC Task Forces, Opportunity Area Expert Groups
- ***Location:*** EOSC Winter School

- *Topics*: to be decided; see examples in Figure 1. When it is important to identify progress over time and/or core obstacles, the topics should remain the same for a couple of years.
- *Duration*: 1 day consisting of
 - 1 x 30 minutes: plenary start: welcome, introductions, goal of the day
 - 4 x 90 minutes: per topic:
 - setting the stage (plenary):
 - share recent developments and discuss challenges (in break-out groups). Benefit from face-to-face options, e.g. brainstorm, use flip charts, paper and pen. Alternatively, if you want to focus on getting many challenges or solutions, rather than on sharing developments among the participants, the World Cafe⁶ approach can be appropriate.
 - share all challenges and add primary stakeholders to address them (plenary).
- *Maximum number of participants*: this basically depends on the number of available break-out rooms. 12 participants is a good number for a group discussion; in a full room probably only a few people will speak up.
- *Roles involved*:
 - Before the event: experts to select the topics, plus experts who can introduce the topic and help steer the discussions
 - During the event: day chair, session chairs, moderators per breakout group, notetakers
 - After the event: notetakers/editors with topical expertise who turn the notes, in particular the challenges plus stakeholders to address them, into a report. This output can range from a blogpost to a 15-page report, which obviously require different efforts.
- *Main differences with the original online Synchronisation Force workshops*:
 - shorter timeframe;
 - more interaction is possible among the participants, thanks to the face-to-face setting;
 - due to the set-up of the Winter School, only a subset of stakeholder categories is involved;
 - there is no chat in parallel to the online workshop, which means missing out on e.g. links and examples, but which is also less distractive.

2. Synchronised Writing Sprint

A writing sprint is a short period of time that is focused purely on writing. This can be an effective approach to involve various stakeholders in highlighting different angles of a complex topic, with a written result. With authors collaborating on a result, this is also called a book sprint⁷.

⁶ <https://theworldcafe.com/key-concepts-resources/world-cafe-method/>

⁷ A good introduction is <https://blog.tib.eu/2018/11/13/how-to-book-sprint-in-sixteen-steps/>

- *Target audience*: all stakeholder groups: European projects, EOSC Task Forces, Opportunity Area Expert Groups, Research Infrastructures, e-Infrastructures, Research Funders, and others.
- *Location*: online
- *Topic*: to be decided; see examples in Figure 1. Given the complexity of these topics and the dynamics of writing sprints it is recommended to focus a sprint on one topic.
- *Duration*: the actual writing sprint can take between 1-3 days. The lead time takes some months, from finding authors to finalising the report.
- *Maximum number of participants*: 15 per sprint, i.e. per topic. The well known Open Science Training Handbook⁸ was written in a sprint by fourteen authors, supported by two facilitators.
- *Roles involved*:
 - Before the event: expert(s) to select the topic
 - During the event: expert authors plus facilitators to guide the process. Facilitation is key.
 - After the event: editors with topical expertise who finalise the report. These could be members from the original author group.
- *Main differences with the original online Synchronisation Force workshops*:
 - the focus is on producing a text which will be more stand-alone and encompassing than a workshop report;
 - far fewer people can participate.

⁸ https://open-science-training-handbook.github.io/Open-Science-Training-Handbook_EN/